

EMS_maize_mutants_BSA_pipeline

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- **Summary:** This pipeline was specially designed in our project to do gene mapping for EMS-induced maize kernel Mutants by using bulked segregant analysis strategy
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- **Website:** https://www.yuque.com/donghx14/lhdk74/hamav6ekn0um4u1t?singleDoc#《EMS_maize_mutants_BSA_pipeline》

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Schematic diagram

B

CHR	POS	REF	ALT	ANN	WP_GT	WP_AD	MP_GT	MP_AD
5	1153 138 94	G	A	Zm00001eb2 35570_T003 c.464C>T p.P ro155Leu	G/A	10,5	A/A	0,17
5	1153 138 00	C	T	Zm00001eb2 35570_T003 c.558G>A p.T rp186*	C/T	17,4	T/T	0,15
5	171 754 578	G	A	Zm00001eb2 42610_T001 c.1933C>T p. Gln645*	G/A	18,11	A/A	0,27

↑ AD1,AD2 ↑

C

SNP-index.	Formula
WP	$WP.AD2 / (WP.AD1 + WP.AD2)$
MP	$MP.AD2 / (MP.AD1 + MP.AD2)$
DELTA	$ (SNP-index.WP) - (SNP-index.MP) $
DIV	$ (SNP-index.WP) - (SNP-index.WP_{Causal}) + (SNP-index.MP) - (SNP-index.MP_{Causal}) $

D

SNP-index.	Recessive			Dominant		
	Range	Causal	Non-causal	Range	Causal	Non-causal
WP	[0-1]	1/3	1/2	[0-1]	0	1/2
MP	[0-1]	1	1/2	[0-1]	2/3	1/2
DELTA	[0-1]	2/3	0	[0-1]	2/3	0
DIV	[0-2]	0	2/3	[0-2]	0	2/3

1.2. How does the pipeline work?

Our EMS_mutants_BSA pipeline could be divided into three steps: (1) sampling & sequencing, (2) variant calling, and (3) association mapping.

For sampling & sequencing, a wild-type pool (WP) and a mutant-type pool (MP) were separately generated from the segregating population, each containing 20–100 individuals. DNAs of each pool were extracted from available embryos, endosperms, or plants. DNAs were then subjected to whole genome sequencing with PE reads, either using illumina or MGI sequencing platform. Finally, four fastq files were finally obtained: WP.1.fq.gz/WP.2.fq.gz for the WP sample, and MP.1.fq.gz/MP.2.fq.gz for the MP sample.

For variant calling, clean reads were aligned to maize Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0 reference genome (Hufford et al. 2021) using BWA (Li and Durbin 2009). Samtools and bcftools (Li et al. 2009) were further used to manipulate alignment files and for variant calling. SnpEff (Cingolani et al. 2012) was used for variant effect annotation. The "VariantsToTable" module in GATK (McKenna et al. 2010) was used to convert the vcf file into a tabular file containing the

following information: chromosome, position, reference allele, alternative allele, genotype, and allelic depth.

For association mapping, a modified "MutMap" method (Abe et al. 2012) was implemented. "SNP-index" was defined as the allele frequency of mutant-type alleles in WP or MP. The equation for calculation is $\text{SNP-index} = (\text{depth of allelic allele}) / (\text{total depth})$. "SNP-index.DIV" was defined as the divergence of SNP-index to theoretical SNP-index for causal mutation. The equation is: $\text{SNP-index.DIV} = | \text{SNP-index.WP} - (\text{theoretical SNP-index.WP for causal}) | + | \text{SNP-index.MP} - (\text{theoretical SNP-index.MP for causal}) |$. For a recessive mutant, the theoretical SNP-index.WP, SNP-index.MP, and SNP-index.DIV for the causal mutation were 1/3, 1, and 0 separately. Genome-wide view of SNP-index.DIV provided a quick scan of the candidate chromosome/region harboring the causal mutation. Markers with SNP-index.DIV < 1/3 were believed to be associated with the trait and were retained for a close-up view. A circos plot was created to show sequencing depth and SNP density using R package circlize (Gu et al. 2014).

1.3. Outputs of this pipeline

- Genome-wide view of SNP-index.WP, SNP-index.MP, and SNP-index.DIV

- Close-up view of SNP-index.DIV and SNP-index.MP with annotations

- A table file containing candidate SNPs

CHR	POS	REF	ALT	ANN	MP.GT	MP.AD	WP.GT	WP.AD	WP.AD1	WP.AD2
	WP.DP	MP.AD1	MP.AD2	MP.DP	snp_index.WP	snp_index.MP	snp_index.DIV			
	snp_index.DELTA	snp_index.MP.loess	snp_index.DIV.loess	impact						
5	24707870	G	A							
A missense_variant MODERATE Zm00001eb220700 Zm00001eb220700 transcript Zm00001eb22										

0700_T001|protein_coding|1/5|c.52C>T|p.Leu18Phe|178/2127|52/1716|18/571||,A|upstream_gene_variant|MODIFIER|Zm00001eb220710|Zm00001eb220710|transcript|Zm00001eb220710_T001|protein_coding||c.-93G>A||||93| A/A 2,23 G/A 15,8 15 8 23 2 23 25
 0.347826086956522 0.92 0.0944927536231884 0.572173913043478 0.875825012971536
 0.211591834969449 MODERATE

5 59295927 G A

A|synonymous_variant|LOW|Zm00001eb227100|Zm00001eb227100|transcript|Zm00001eb227100_T001|protein_coding|2/14|c.153G>A|p.Ala51Ala|857/4518|153/3459|51/1152||,A|upstream_gene_variant|MODIFIER|Zm00001eb227100|Zm00001eb227100|transcript|Zm00001eb227100_T002|protein_coding||n.-1430G>A||||1430|,A|upstream_gene_variant|MODIFIER|Zm00001eb227100|Zm00001eb227100|transcript|Zm00001eb227100_T003|protein_coding||n.-1430G>A||||1430| A/A 0,17
 G/A 12,5 12 5 17 0 17 17 0.294117647058824 1
 0.0392156862745098 0.705882352941176 0.945007169456415 0.142070428416798
 LOW

5 115313894 G A

A|missense_variant|MODERATE|Zm00001eb235570|Zm00001eb235570|transcript|Zm00001eb235570_T003|protein_coding|2/4|c.464C>T|p.Pro155Leu|569/1740|464/1314|155/437|| A/A 0,17
 G/A 10,5 10 5 15 0 17 17 0.3333333333333333 1 0
 0.6666666666666667 0.996738848696962 0.0904115477538818 MODERATE

5 136346910 G A

A|splice_acceptor_variant&intron_variant|HIGH|Zm00001eb237290|Zm00001eb237290|transcript|Zm00001eb237290_T001|protein_coding|1/2|c.199-1G>A||||| A/A 1,20 G/A 18,5 18 5
 23 1 20 21 0.217391304347826 0.952380952380952 0.163561076604555
 0.734989648033126 0.989542869027246 0.104117666744335 HIGH

5 138344910 G A

A|missense_variant|MODERATE|DAAT_0|Zm00001eb237500|transcript|Zm00001eb237500_T004|protein_coding|4/5|c.1006G>A|p.Glu336Lys|1083/1601|1006/1251|336/416||,A|intron_variant|MODIFIER|DAAT_0|Zm00001eb237500|transcript|Zm00001eb237500_T005|protein_coding|1/1|n.325-659G>A||||| A/A 0,28 G/A 19,10 19 10 29 0 28 28 0.344827586206897 1
 0.0114942528735633 0.655172413793103 0.988521814464024 0.106656724025104
 MODERATE

- A circos plot showing sequencing depth and SNP density

- Statistics of SNP numbers and types.

Distribution of Detected SNPs

Type of Detected SNPs

Distribution of Filtered SNPs

Type of Filtered SNPs

2. PRE-REQUIREMENTS

2.1. Software

- Alignment & Variant calling
 - gtfSORT, bwa, samtools, bcftools, gatk, vcftools, bedtools, picard, snpeff
- Python packages:
 - pandas, argparse, csv
- R packages:
 - circlize

2.2. self-written scripts

- `filter_longest_cds_from_gtf.py`

```
1 import pandas as pd
2 import argparse
3 import csv
4
5 def parse_gtf(gtf_file):
6     # read GTF file
7     gtf = pd.read_csv(gtf_file, sep='\t', comment='#', header=None)
8     gtf.columns = ['seqname', 'source', 'feature', 'start', 'end', 'score'
9 , 'strand', 'frame', 'attribute']
10     return gtf
11
12 def filter_cds(gtf):
13     # filter rows with "cds" feature
14     return gtf[gtf['feature'] == 'CDS'].copy()
15
16 def find_longest_cds(cds_gtf):
17     # extract gene_id and transcript_id
18     cds_gtf['gene_id'] = cds_gtf['attribute'].str.extract('gene_id "([^\n
19 +)"+)')
20     cds_gtf['transcript_id'] = cds_gtf['attribute'].str.extract('transcrip
21 t_id "([^\n]+)"+)')
22     cds_info = cds_gtf[['gene_id', 'transcript_id', 'start', 'end']]
23
24     # calculate cds length for each transcript
25     cds_info['cds_length'] = cds_info['end'] - cds_info['start'] + 1
26     cds_lengths = cds_info.groupby(['gene_id', 'transcript_id'])['cds_leng
27 th'].sum().reset_index()
28
29     # find the longest cds for each gene
30     return cds_lengths.loc[cds_lengths.groupby('gene_id')['cds_length'].id
31 xmax()]
32
33 def filter_original_gtf(original_gtf, longest_cds):
34     # filter original GTF file
35     longest_gene_ids = longest_cds['gene_id'].unique()
36     longest_transcript_ids = longest_cds['transcript_id'].unique()
37
38     # create filter conditions
39     gene_condition = original_gtf['attribute'].str.contains('|'.join(longe
40 st_gene_ids)) & (original_gtf['feature'] == 'gene')
41     transcript_condition = original_gtf['attribute'].str.contains('|'.join
42 (longest_gene_ids)) & original_gtf['attribute'].str.contains('|'.join(long
43 est_transcript_ids))
44
45     # merge two conditions
```

```

38     filtered_gtf = original_gtf[gene_condition | transcript_condition]
39
40     return filtered_gtf
41
42 def save_results(longest_cds, filtered_gtf, out_prefix):
43     # output results to files
44     longest_cds[['gene_id', 'transcript_id', 'cds_length']].to_csv(
45         f"{out_prefix}.longest_cds.id.table", index=False, header=False, s
46     ep='\t', quoting=csv.QUOTE_NONE)
47     filtered_gtf.to_csv(f"{out_prefix}.longest_cds.gtf", sep='\t', index=F
48     else, header=False, quoting=csv.QUOTE_NONE)
49
50 def main(gtf_file, out_prefix):
51     original_gtf = parse_gtf(gtf_file)
52     cds_gtf = filter_cds(original_gtf)
53
54     longest_cds = find_longest_cds(cds_gtf)
55     filtered_gtf = filter_original_gtf(original_gtf, longest_cds)
56
57     save_results(longest_cds, filtered_gtf, out_prefix)
58
59 if __name__ == "__main__":
60     parser = argparse.ArgumentParser(description='Process GTF file to fin
61     d longest cds transcripts.')
62     parser.add_argument('--gtf', required=True, help='Input GTF file')
63     parser.add_argument('--out_prefix', required=True, help='Output file p
64     refix')
65     args = parser.parse_args()
66
67     main(args.gtf, args.out_prefix)

```

2.3. Reference genome

Maize reference genome (B73V5) could be downloaded from Ensembl-Plants (<https://plants.ensembl.org/index.html>), Phytozome (<https://phytozome-next.jgi.doe.gov/>), MaizeGDB (<https://maizegdb.org/>), NCBI (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), etc.

To speed up, we only kept main chromosomes (1–10), and discard Pt, Mt, and all other short scaffolds. Also, we extracted the longest_cds transcript for each in the gtf file. The following code shows how we manipulate the reference genome.

```
1 #-----
2 # Setup directories and variables
3 # Adjust according to needs
4 #-----
5
6 ref_Dir=/data/x1005/Case/EMS_mutants_BSA/REFERENCE/maize_B73V5_BSA # Direc
7 tory containing reference genome files
8 snpEff_Dir=/data/x1005/biosoft/snpEff # Path to snpEff tools
9 script_Dir=/data/x1005/biosoft/self_scripts # Path to self-written scripts
10
11 ref_prefix=maize_B73V5_BSA # Prefix used for naming files related to the r
12 eference genome
13
14 #-----
15 # Download reference genome
16 # Adjust according to needs
17 #-----
18
19 # Download FASTA files for chromosomes 1 to 10
20 for i in {1..10}; do wget https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/ensemblgenomes/pub/release
21 -60/plants/fasta/zea_mays/dna/Zea_mays.Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0.dna.chromo
22 some.${i}.fa.gz ./ ; done
23
24 # Concatenate all chromosomes into a single FASTA file
25 for i in {1..10}; do gunzip -c Zea_mays.Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0.dna.chrom
26 osome.${i}.fa.gz >> ${ref_prefix}.fasta; done
27
28 # Download GTF file
29 wget https://ftp.ebi.ac.uk/ensemblgenomes/pub/release-60/plants/gtf/zea_ma
30 ys/Zea_mays.Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0.60.chr.gtf.gz ./
31 gunzip -c Zea_mays.Zm-B73-REFERENCE-NAM-5.0.60.chr.gtf.gz > ${ref_prefix}.
32 original.gtf
33
34 #-----
35 # Process reference genome
36 #-----
37
38 # Sort the GTF file
39 gtf2gene -i ${ref_prefix}.original.gtf -o ${ref_prefix}.sorted.gtf -t 10
40
41 # Extract longest CDS from the GTF file
42 python ${script_Dir}/filter_longest_cds_from_gtf.py --gtf ${ref_prefix}.so
43 rted.gtf --out_prefix ${ref_prefix}
```

```

38
39
40 # Rename the output GTF file
41 mv ${ref_prefix}.longest_cds.gtf ${ref_prefix}.gtf
42
43 #-----
44 ## Build index files for reference genome
45 #-----
46
47 # Build BWA index
48 bwa index ${ref_prefix}.fasta -p ${ref_prefix}
49
50 # Create a sequence index with SAMtools
51 samtools faidx ${ref_prefix}.fasta
52
53 # Create a sequence dictionary with Picard
54 picard CreateSequenceDictionary R=${ref_prefix}.fasta O=${ref_prefix}.dict
55
56 # Extract chromosome lengths
57 cut -f 1,2 ${prefix}.fasta.fai > chr.lens.txt
58
59
60 #-----
61 ## Build database for snpEff
62 #-----
63
64 snpEff_Dir=/data/x1005/biosoft/snpEff # Path to snpEff tools
65
66 # Create the directory for snpEff database
67 mkdir -p ${snpEff_Dir}/data/${prefix}/
68
69 # Copy FASTA and GTF files to snpEff
70 cp ${ref_Dir}/${prefix}.fasta ${snpEff_Dir}/data/${prefix}/sequences.fasta
71 cp ${ref_Dir}/${prefix}.gtf ${snpEff_Dir}/data/${prefix}/genes.gtf
72
73 # Update snpEff configuration
74 echo "${prefix}.genome : ${prefix}" >> ${snpEff_Dir}/snpEff.config
75
76 # Build snpEff database
77 java -jar ${snpEff_Dir}/snpEff.jar build -c ${snpEff_Dir}/snpEff.config -g
78 tf22 -v ${prefix}
79

```

3. RUNNING

3.1. Variant calling

```
1 #####
2 # Step 1. Set up directories and ariables
3 # Modify the variables according to your project requirements
4 #####
5
6 sample=B73KM4 # Sample name
7 work_Dir=/data/x1005/Case/EMS_mutants_BSA/${sample} # Working directory f
or output and intermediate files
8 fastq_Dir=/data/x1005/Case/EMS_mutants_BSA/${sample}/FASTQ # Directory co
ntaining FASTQ files
9 ref_Dir=/data/x1005/Case/EMS_mutants_BSA/REFERENCE/maize_B73V5_BSA # Dire
ctory containing reference genome files
10 snpEff_Dir=/data/x1005/biosoft/snpEff # Path to snpEff tools
11 script_Dir=/data/x1005/biosoft/self_scripts # Path to self-written script
s
12
13 ref_prefix=maize_B73V5_BSA # Prefix for reference genome files
14 WP1=WGS.${sample}_WP.1.fq.gz # Pair-end sequencing file 1 for WP
15 WP2=WGS.${sample}_WP.2.fq.gz # Pair-end sequencing file 2 for WP
16 MP1=WGS.${sample}_MP.1.fq.gz # Pair-end sequencing file 1 for MP
17 MP2=WGS.${sample}_MP.2.fq.gz # Pair-end sequencing file 2 for MP
18
19 threads=48 # Number of CPU threads to use for parallel processing
20 ws=1000000 # Window size for coverage and density analysis
21
22 cd ${work_Dir} # Change to the working directory
23
24
25 #####
26 # Step 2. Prepare Reference Genome and Sequencing Data
27 #####
28
29 # Create symbolic links to reference genome files
30 ln -s ${ref_Dir}/${ref_prefix}.* ./
31
32 # Create symbolic links to sequencing data files
33 ln -s ${fastq_Dir}/${WP1} WP.1.fq.gz
34 ln -s ${fastq_Dir}/${WP2} WP.2.fq.gz
35 ln -s ${fastq_Dir}/${MP1} MP.1.fq.gz
36 ln -s ${fastq_Dir}/${MP2} MP.2.fq.gz
37
```

```

38 #####
39 #####
40 # Step 3. Alignment
41 #####
42 #####
43 # Align WP (wild-type pool) data using BWA MEM, followed by post-processing
44 # with SAMtools
45 bwa mem -t ${threads} \
46   -R '@RG\tID:WP\tSM:WP\tPL:illumina' \
47   ${ref_prefix} \
48   WP.1.fq.gz \
49   WP.2.fq.gz 2> WP.bwa.log | \
50 samtools fixmate -m - - | \
51 samtools sort -@ ${threads} -m 1G | \
52 samtools markdup - WP.sort.markdup.bam
53
54 # Index and generate alignment statistics for WP
55 samtools index WP.sort.markdup.bam
56 samtools flagstat WP.sort.markdup.bam > WP.sort.markdup.bam.flagstat
57 samtools coverage WP.sort.markdup.bam > WP.sort.markdup.bam.coverage
58
59 # Align MP (mutant-type pool) data using BWA MEM, followed by post-processing
60 # with SAMtools
61 bwa mem -t ${threads} \
62   -R '@RG\tID:MP\tSM:MP\tPL:illumina' \
63   ${ref_prefix} \
64   MP.1.fq.gz \
65   MP.2.fq.gz 2> MP.bwa.log | \
66 samtools fixmate -m - - | \
67 samtools sort -@ ${threads} -m 1G | \
68 samtools markdup - MP.sort.markdup.bam
69
70 # Index and generate alignment statistics for MP
71 samtools index MP.sort.markdup.bam
72 samtools flagstat MP.sort.markdup.bam > MP.sort.markdup.bam.flagstat
73 samtools coverage MP.sort.markdup.bam > MP.sort.markdup.bam.coverage
74
75 #####
76 # Step 4. Variant Calling
77 #####
78
79 # Create a list of BAM files for variant calling
80 echo "\

```

```

80 WP.sort.markdup.bam
81 MP.sort.markdup.bam \
82 " > bam.list
83
84 # Perform mpileup and call variants using bcftools
85 bcftools mpileup \
86   --bam-list bam.list \
87   --annotate DP,AD,ADF,ADR \
88   --threads ${threads} \
89   --no-BAQ \
90   --min-MQ 40 \
91   --min-BQ 18 \
92   --adjust-MQ 50 \
93   --output-type u \
94   --fasta-ref ${ref_prefix}.fasta | \
95 bcftools call \
96   --threads ${threads} \
97   --multiallelic-caller \
98   --annotate GQ,GP \
99   --variants-only \
100  --output-type v \
101  --output all.raw.vcf
102
103 # Filter variants based on mapping quality (MQ) and quality score (QUAL)
104 bcftools filter \
105   -i 'INFO/MQ>=40 && QUAL>20' \
106   -O v \
107   -o all.filter.vcf \
108   all.raw.vcf
109
110 # Extract SNP variants from the filtered VCF file
111 bcftools view \
112   --samples WP,MP \
113   --types snps \
114   --output-type v \
115   --output snp.filter.vcf \
116   all.filter.vcf
117
118 # Alternative step to extract INDEL variants
119 # bcftools view \
120 #   --sample WP,MP \
121 #   --types indels \
122 #   --output-type v \
123 #   --output indel.filter.vcf \
124 #   all.filter.vcf
125
126 # Perform additional filtration of SNP variants using vcftools
127 vcftools \

```

```

128     --vcf snp.filter.vcf \
129     --max-missing 1 \
130     --min-alleles 2 \
131     --max-alleles 2 \
132     --minDP 4 --maxDP 100 \
133     --recode --recode-INFO-all \
134     --out snp
135
136
137     #####
138     #####
139     # Step 5. Variant Annotation
140     #####
141     #####
142     # Annotate the filtered SNP VCF file using snpEff for functional annotations
143     java -jar ${snpEff_Dir}/snpEff.jar eff -ud 2000 maize_B73V5_BSA snp.recode.vcf > snp.anno.vcf
144
145     #####
146     #####
147     # Step 6. Convert vcf to table
148     #####
149     #####
150     # Use GATK to convert the VCF file to a table with selected columns
151     gatk VariantsToTable \
152     -R ${ref_prefix}.fasta \
153     -V snp.anno.vcf \
154     -F CHROM -F POS -F REF -F ALT -F ANN -GF GT -GF AD \
155     -O snp.table
156
157     #####
158     #####
159     # Step 7. Statistics on sequencing depth
160     #####
161     #####
162     # Generate a list of genomic windows with specified window size
163     bedtools makewindows -g ${ref_prefix}.fasta.fai -w ${ws} > windows.bed
164
165     # Calculate sequencing depth across windows for WP and MP alignments
166     samtools bedcov windows.bed WP.sort.markdup.bam > WP.depth.bed
167     samtools bedcov windows.bed MP.sort.markdup.bam > MP.depth.bed

```

3.2. Association mapping

3.2.1. bsa.R

```
1 # Load essential packages
2 library(ggplot2)
3 library(tidyverse)
4
5 # Define color scheme for visualization
6 ten_colors <- c("#E64B35", "#4DBBD5", "#00A087", "#3C5488", "#F39B7F", "#
8491B4", "#91D1C2", "#DC0000", "#7E6148", "#B09C85")
7
8 col.red <- ten_colors[1]
9 col.blue <- ten_colors[2]
10 col.green <- ten_colors[3]
11 col.orange <- ten_colors[5]
12
13 col.gray <- "#777777"
14 col.black <- "#312a22"
15
16 #####
17 # Step 1. Load data
18 #####
19
20 # Load SNP table
21 snp <- read.delim("snp.table", header = TRUE, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)
22 colnames(snp) <- c("CHR", "POS", "REF", "ALT", "ANN",
23 "MP.GT", "MP.AD", "WP.GT", "WP.AD")
24
25 #####
26 # step 2. SNP-index calculation
27 #####
28
29 # Calculate allelic depth for the Wild-type pool (WP)
30
31 snp$WP.AD1 <- sapply(snp$WP.AD, function(x){
32   a <- as.numeric(unlist(strsplit(x, ",")))
33   b <- a[1] # First value is the reference allele depth
34   return(b)
35 })
36
37 snp$WP.AD2 <- sapply(snp$WP.AD, function(x){
38   a <- as.numeric(unlist(strsplit(x, ",")))
39   b <- a[length(a)] # Last value is the alternate allele depth
40   return(b)
```

```

41   })
42
43   # Total depth for WP
44   snp$WP.DP <- snp$WP.AD1 + snp$WP.AD2
45
46   # Calculate allelic depth for the Mutant-type pool (MP)
47   snp$MP.AD1 <- sapply(snp$MP.AD, function(x){
48     a <- as.numeric(unlist(strsplit(x, ",")))
49     b <- a[1] # First value is the reference allele depth
50     return(b)
51   })
52
53   snp$MP.AD2 <- sapply(snp$MP.AD, function(x){
54     a <- as.numeric(unlist(strsplit(x, ",")))
55     b <- a[length(a)] # Last value is the alternate allele depth
56     return(b)
57   })
58
59   # Total depth for MP
60   snp$MP.DP <- snp$MP.AD1 + snp$MP.AD2
61
62   # Calculate SNP-index for WP and MP
63   snp$snp_index.WP <- snp$WP.AD2 / snp$WP.DP
64   snp$snp_index.MP <- snp$MP.AD2 / snp$MP.DP
65
66   # Calculate divergence (absolute difference from theoretical values for causal mutation)
67   snp$snp_index.DIV <- abs(snp$snp_index.WP - 1/3) + abs(snp$snp_index.MP - 1) # Adjust the theoretical values accordingly
68   snp$snp_index.DELTA <- abs(snp$snp_index.WP - snp$snp_index.MP)
69
70   # Save the resulting data in an RData file
71   save(snp, file="snp.rdata")
72
73
74   #####
75   #####
76   # step 3. Genome-wide visualization
77   #####
78   #####
79   # chr.lens <- read.delim("chr.lens.txt", header = F, stringsAsFactors = F)
80   # colnames(chr.lens) <- c("chr", "len")
81
82   # Create a data frame with chromosome lengths
83   chr.lens <- data.frame(
      chr = 1:10,

```

```

84     len = c(308452471, 243675191, 238017767, 250330460, 226353449,
85             181357234, 185808916, 182411202, 163004744, 152435371)
86 )
87
88 # Create color vector for alternating colors
89 color.vector <- rep(c(col.orange, col.blue), length.out = nrow(chr.lens))
90
91 # Calculate cumulative start, end, and mean positions for each chromosome
92 chr.lens$acc.start <- cumsum(chr.lens$len) - chr.lens$len + 1
93 chr.lens$acc.end <- cumsum(chr.lens$len)
94 chr.lens$acc.mean <- (chr.lens$acc.start + chr.lens$acc.end) / 2
95
96 # Define the manhattan plot function using ggplot2
97 manhattan_ggplot <- function(chr, pos, value, value.curve = NULL, ylim =
98   c(0, 1), ylab = "SNP-index", abline_h = NULL){
99
100   # Combine input data into a data frame
101   df <- data.frame(chr = factor(chr), pos = pos, value = value)
102
103   # Adjust positions for cumulative chromosome lengths
104   df$pos_new <- df$pos + chr.lens$acc.start[match(df$chr, chr.lens$chr)]
105   - 1
106
107   # Create the ggplot object
108   p <- ggplot(df, aes(x = pos_new, y = value, color = chr)) +
109     geom_point(size = 1) +
110     scale_color_manual(values = color.vector) + # Use the color vector
111     labs(x = NULL, y = ylab, title = NULL) +
112     theme_minimal() +
113     theme(
114       axis.title.x = element_blank(), # Remove x-axis title
115       legend.position = "none",      # Remove the legend
116     ) +
117     ylim(ylim) +
118     scale_x_continuous(
119       breaks = chr.lens$acc.mean,
120       labels = paste0("chr", chr.lens$chr)
121     )
122
123   # Add a horizontal line (optional)
124   if (!is.null(abline_h)) {
125     p <- p + geom_hline(yintercept = abline_h, linetype = "dashed", color
126       = "black", size = 0.5)
127   }
128
129   # Optionally add curve to the plot if provided
130   if (!is.null(value.curve)) {

```

```

129     df_curve <- data.frame(chr = chr, pos = pos, value_curve = value.curv
130     e)
131     df_curve$pos_new <- df_curve$pos + chr.lens$acc.start[match(df_curve
132     $chr, chr.lens$chr)] - 1
133     p <- p + geom_line(data = df_curve, aes(x = pos_new, y = value_curv
134     e), color = "black", size = 0.5)
135     }
136     # Print the plot
137     print(p)
138     return(df$pos_new) # Return adjusted positions
139   }
140   # Plot SNP-index for Wild-type pool (WP)
141   png("Genome-wide.SNP-index.WP.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "in",
142   res = 300)
143   pos.new <- manhattan_ggplot(chr = snp$CHR, pos = snp$POS, value = snp$s
144   np_index.WP, ylim = c(0, 1), ylab = "SNP-index.WP")
145   dev.off()
146   # Plot SNP-index for Mutant-type pool (MP)
147   png("Genome-wide.SNP-index.MP.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "in",
148   res = 300)
149   pos.new <- manhattan_ggplot(chr = snp$CHR, pos = snp$POS, value = snp$s
150   np_index.MP, ylim = c(0, 1), ylab = "SNP-index.MP")
151   dev.off()
152   # Plot SNP-index for Delta
153   png("Genome-wide.SNP-index.DELTA.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "i
154   n", res = 300)
155   pos.new <- manhattan_ggplot(chr = snp$CHR, pos = snp$POS, value = snp$s
156   np_index.DELTA, ylim = c(0, 1), ylab = "SNP-index.DELTA")
157   dev.off()
158   # Plot SNP-index for DIV (Genome-wide)
159   png("Genome-wide.SNP-index.DIV.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "in"
160   , res = 300)
161   pos.new <- manhattan_ggplot(chr = snp$CHR, pos = snp$POS, value = snp$s
162   np_index.DIV, ylim = c(0, 1), ylab = "SNP-index.DIV", abline_h = 1/3)
163   dev.off()
164
165   #####
166   #####
167   # step 4. Close-up visualization
168   #####
169   #####

```

```

164
165 # Filter SNPs based on SNP-index.DIV < 1/3
166 condition <- snp$snp_index.DIV < 1/3
167 snp_filter <- snp[condition, ]
168
169 # Find chromosome harboring causal mutation (most SNPs in filtered set)
170 chr.causal <- names(sort(table(snp_filter$CHR), decreasing = TRUE))[1]
171
172 # Filter SNPs for this causal chromosome
173 condition <- snp_filter$CHR == as.numeric(chr.causal)
174 snp_final <- snp_filter[condition, ]
175
176 # Perform LOESS smoothing
177 f <- 2/3 # smoothing parameter
178 snp_final$snp_index.MP.loess <- unlist(lowess(x = snp_final$POS, y = snp_
179 final$snp_index.MP, f = f)$y)
180 snp_final$snp_index.DIV.loess <- unlist(lowess(x = snp_final$POS, y = snp_
181 _final$snp_index.DIV, f = f)$y)
182
183 # Condition based on impact
184 condition.modifier <- grepl(pattern = "MODIFIER", x = snp_final$ANN, per
185 l = TRUE)
186 condition.low <- grepl(pattern = "LOW", x = snp_final$ANN, perl = TRUE)
187 condition.moderate <- grepl(pattern = "MODERATE", x = snp_final$ANN, per
188 l = TRUE)
189 condition.high <- grepl(pattern = "HIGH", x = snp_final$ANN, perl = TRUE)
190
191 # Convert to a data frame suitable for ggplot
192 snp_final$impact <- ifelse(condition.high, "HIGH",
193 ifelse(condition.moderate, "MODERATE",
194 ifelse(condition.low, "LOW", "MODIFIE
195 R")))
196 snp_final$impact <- factor(snp_final$impact, levels = c("MODIFIER", "LOW"
197 , "MODERATE", "HIGH"))
198
199 ## Plot 1: SNP-index.MP chromosome visualization
200 ggplot(snp_final, aes(x = POS)) +
201   geom_point(aes(y = snp_index.MP, color = impact, shape = impact, size =
202 impact)) + # Plot SNP points
203   # geom_smooth(aes(y = snp_index.MP.loess), method = "loess", se = FALS
204 E, color = "black", size = 1) + # LOESS smoothed line
205   geom_line(aes(x = POS, y = snp_index.MP.loess), color = "black", size =
206 0.5) + # LOESS smoothed line
207   geom_hline(yintercept = 0.9, linetype = "dashed", color = "black", siz
208 e = 0.5) + # Horizontal threshold line
209   geom_vline(xintercept = snp_final$POS[which.max(snp_final$snp_index.MP.
210 loess)], linetype = "dashed", color = "black", size = 0.5) + # Vertical
211 line for causal mutation

```

```

200   scale_color_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = "lightgray", "LOW" = col.blu
e, "MODERATE" = col.orange, "HIGH" = col.red)) + # Color mapping
201   scale_shape_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = 1, "LOW" = 19, "MODERATE" =
19, "HIGH" = 19)) + # Shape mapping
202   scale_size_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = 1, "LOW" = 2, "MODERATE" = 2
, "HIGH" = 2)) + # Size mapping
203   labs(x = NULL, y = "SNP-index.MP", title = NULL) +
204   theme_minimal() +
205   theme(legend.title = element_blank(), legend.position = "right")
206
207 # Save plot to a PNG file
208 ggsave("Chromosome.SNP-index.MP.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "in"
, dpi = 300)
209
210
211 ## Plot 2: SNP-index.DIV chromosome visualization
212 ggplot(snp_final, aes(x = POS)) +
213   geom_point(aes(y = snp_index.DIV, color = impact, shape = impact, size
= impact)) + # Plot SNP points
214   # geom_smooth(aes(y = snp_index.DIV.loess), method = "loess", se = FALS
E, color = "black", size = 1) + # LOESS smoothed line
215   geom_line(aes(y = snp_index.DIV.loess), color = "black", size = 0.5) +
# LOESS smoothed line
216   geom_hline(yintercept = 0.1, linetype = "dashed", color = "black", siz
e = 0.5) + # Horizontal threshold line
217   geom_vline(xintercept = snp_final$POS[which.min(snp_final$snp_index.DI
V.loess)], linetype = "dashed", color = "black", size = 0.5) + # Vertica
l line for causal mutation
218   scale_color_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = "lightgray", "LOW" = col.blu
e, "MODERATE" = col.orange, "HIGH" = col.red)) + # Color mapping
219   scale_shape_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = 1, "LOW" = 19, "MODERATE" =
19, "HIGH" = 19)) + # Shape mapping
220   scale_size_manual(values = c("MODIFIER" = 1, "LOW" = 2, "MODERATE" = 2
, "HIGH" = 2)) + # Size mapping
221   labs(x = NULL, y = "SNP-index.DIV", title = NULL) +
222   theme_minimal() +
223   theme(legend.title = element_blank(), legend.position = "right")
224
225 # Save plot to a PNG file
226 ggsave("Chromosome.SNP-index.DIV.png", width = 6, height = 3, units = "i
n", dpi = 300)
227
228
229
230 #####
231 #####
# step 5. Output candidate

```

```

232 #####
233 #####
234
235 # Apply filtering to select potential candidates
236 condition <- (snp_final$snp_index.MP > 0.9) & (condition.low | condition.
237 moderate | condition.high)
238 candidate <- snp_final[condition, ]
239
240 # Output candidates to file
241 write.table(candidate, file = "Candidate.txt", sep = "\t", col.names =
T, row.names = F, quote = F)
242
243 #####
244 # step 6. SNP density calculation
245 #####
246 #####
247 # SNP density calculation function
248 snp_density <- function(chr.len, snp, ws) {
249   # chr.len: Data frame containing chromosome length information
250   # snp: Data frame containing SNP information (chr and position)
251   # ws: Window size (number of base pairs in each window)
252
253   colnames(chr.len) <- c("chr", "length")
254   colnames(snp) <- c("chr", "position")
255
256   # List to store results
257   result <- list()
258
259   # Loop over each chromosome
260   for (i in 1:nrow(chr.len)) {
261     chr_name <- chr.len$chr[i]      # Current chromosome
262     chr_length <- chr.len$length[i] # Chromosome length
263
264     # Create window start positions
265     start_positions <- seq(1, chr_length, by = ws)
266     end_positions <- pmin(start_positions + ws - 1, chr_length)
267
268     # Filter SNPs by chromosome
269     chr_snp <- snp[snp$chr == chr_name, ]
270
271     # Count SNPs in each window
272     snp_counts <- sapply(1:length(start_positions), function(j) {
273       sum(chr_snp$position >= start_positions[j] & chr_snp$position <= en
274         d_positions[j])
275     })

```

```

275
276     # Create a result data frame for the current chromosome
277     chr_result <- data.frame(
278         chr = chr_name,
279         start = start_positions,
280         end = end_positions,
281         snp_count = snp_counts
282     )
283
284     # Store the result in the list
285     result[[chr_name]] <- chr_result
286 }
287
288 # Combine results from all chromosomes
289 final_result <- do.call(rbind, result)
290
291 return(final_result)
292 }
293
294 # Compute SNP counts for all SNPs and filtered SNPs
295 snp.count <- snp_density(chr.lens, snp[, 1:2], ws = 1000000)
296 snp_filter.count <- snp_density(chr.lens, snp_filter[, 1:2], ws = 1000000)
297 )
298
299 # Write the SNP count results to bed files
300 write.table(snp.count, file="snp.count.bed", quote=F, sep="\t", col.names
301 =F, row.names=F)
302 write.table(snp_filter.count, file="snp_filter.count.bed", quote=F, sep=
303 "\t", col.names=F, row.names=F)
304
305 #####
306 #####
307 # step 7. Statistics on SNP numbers and types
308 #####
309 #####
310
311 # 创建数据框
312 snp.number <- table(snp$CHR)
313
314 snp_filter.number <- table(snp_filter$CHR)
315
316 snp.type <- sort(table(paste0(snp$REF, ">", snp$ALT)), decreasing = T)
317
318 snp_filter.type <- sort(table(paste0(snp_filter$REF, ">", snp_filter$ALT
319 )), decreasing = T)
320
321 # 绘制饼图

```

```

317
318 png("snp.number.png", width = 5, height = 5, unit = "in", res = 300)
319 pie(snp.number, labels = paste0("chr", names(snp.number), " (" , snp.numbe
320 r, ")"), main = "Distribution of Detected SNPs", col = ten_colors)
321 dev.off()

322 #
323 png("snp_filter.number.png", width = 5, height = 5, unit = "in", res = 30
324 0)
325 pie(snp_filter.number, labels = paste0("chr", names(snp_filter.number),
326 " (" , snp_filter.number, ")"), main = "Distribution of Filtered SNPs", co
327 l = ten_colors)
328 dev.off()

329 #
330 png("snp.type.png", width = 5, height = 5, unit = "in", res = 300)
331 pie(snp.type, labels = paste0(names(snp.type), " (" , snp.type, ")"), mai
332 n = "Type of Detected SNPs", col = ten_colors)
333 dev.off()

334 #
335 png("snp_filter.type.png", width = 5, height = 5, unit = "in", res = 300)
336 pie(snp_filter.type, labels = paste0(names(snp_filter.type), " (" , snp_fi
337 lter.type, ")"), main = "Type of Filtered SNPs", col = ten_colors)
338 dev.off()

```

3.2.2. circos.R

```
1 library(circlize)
2
3 # Define color scheme for visualization
4 ten_colors <- c("#E64B35", "#4DBBD5", "#00A087", "#3C5488", "#F39B7F", "#
5 8491B4", "#91D1C2", "#DC0000", "#7E6148", "#B09C85")
6
7 col.red <- ten_colors[1]
8 col.blue <- ten_colors[2]
9 col.green <- ten_colors[3]
10 col.orange <- ten_colors[5]
11 col.gray <- "lightgray"
12
13 # Set plot parameters
14 bg.border <- NA
15 track.height <- 0.17 # Adjust based on performance
16
17 #-----
18 # Chromosome information
19 #-----
20
21 # chr.lens <- read.delim(chr.lens.txt, header = FALSE, stringsAsFactors
22 = FALSE)
23 # colnames(chr.lens) <- c("chr", "length", "factors")
24
25 # Example chromosome lengths (replace with your actual data if needed)
26 chr.lens <- data.frame(chr = 1:10, length = c(308452471, 243675191, 23801
27 7767, 250330460, 226353449, 181357234, 185808916, 182411202, 163004744, 1
28 52435371))
29 chr.lens$factors <- 1:nrow(chr.lens)
30
31 # Initialize circular layout with a gap for separation
32 chr.layout <- rbind(chr.lens, data.frame(chr = chr.lens$chr, length = rep
33 (0, nrow(chr.lens)), factors = chr.lens$factors, stringsAsFactors = FALS
34 E))
35 chr_gap.layout <- rbind(chr.layout, data.frame(chr = rep("gap", 2), lengt
36 h = c(0, min(chr.lens$length)), factors = rep(nrow(chr.lens) + 1, 2), str
37 ingsAsFactors = FALSE))
38
39 #-----
40 # Plot start: Create Circular Plot
41 #-----
42
43 # Save plot as PNG file
```

```

38 png("Circos.png", width = 6, height = 6, unit = "in", res = 300)
39
40 # Set Circos parameters for the plot
41 circos.par(cell.padding = c(0.02, 0.1, 0.02, 0.1))
42 circos.initialize(factors = chr_gap.layout$factors, x = chr_gap.layout$le
43 ngth)
44
45 #-----
46 # Plot the outer track (chromosomes and labels)
47 #-----
48
49 ylim <- c(0, 1)
50 track.index <- 1
51
52 # Set track height and initialize
53 circos.par("track.height" = 0.08)
54 circos.track(bg.col = NA, bg.border = bg.border, track.margin = c(0, 0),
55 factors = chr.layout$factors, ylim = ylim)
56
57 # Plot chromosomes as rectangles
58 for(i in 1:nrow(chr.lens)){
59   circos.rect(border = NA, xleft = 1, xright = chr.lens$length[i], ybotto
60 m = 0, ytop = 1, col = col.gray, track.index = track.index, sector.index
61 = chr.lens$factors[i])
62 }
63
64 # Add labels and scale ticks for chromosomes
65 for(i in 1:nrow(chr.lens)){
66   chr.len <- chr.layout$length[i]
67   circos.text(x = chr.len/2, y = ylim[2]/2, facing = "inside", cex = 1, f
68 ont = 2, labels = paste0("Chr", chr.layout$chr[i]), track.index = track.i
69 ndex, sector.index = chr.lens$factors[i])
70
71   major.at <- seq(0, chr.len + 1e8, 1e8) # Adjust based on genome size
72   major.labels <- paste0(major.at / 1e6, "MB") # Adjust based on genome s
73 ize.
74   circos.axis(labels.cex = 0.75, major.at = major.at, labels = major.labe
75 ls, labels.niceFacing = T, sector.index = chr.lens$factors[i])
76 }
77
78 #-----
79 # Plot sequencing depth for WP
80 #-----
81
82 bed <- read.delim("WP.depth.bed", header = FALSE, stringsAsFactors = FALS
83 E)

```

```

77 colnames.bed) <- c("chr", "start", "end", "count")
78 bed$factoꖑ <- chr.lens$factoꖑ[match.bed$chr, chr.lens$chr]]
79 bed$count <- bed$count / (bed$end - bed$start)
80
81 # Apply limits
82 ylim <- c(0, 50) # Adjust based on sequencing depth
83 bed$count[bed$count > ylim[2]] <- ylim[2]
84 bed$count[bed$count < ylim[1]] <- ylim[1]
85
86 # Add new track for WP sequencing depth
87 track.index <- track.index + 1
88 circos.par("track.height" = track.height)
89 circos.track(bg.border = bg.border, track.margin = c(0.01, 0), factors =
90 chr.layout$factoꖑ, ylim = ylim)
91
92 # Plot the data as lines on the track
93 circos.trackLines(factors = bed$factoꖑ, x = rowMeans.bed[, c("start", "e
94 nd"))], y = bed$count, lwd = 1.2, col = col.green)
95 circos.yaxis(side = "left", at=c(ylim[1], mean(ylim), ylim[2]), sector.in
96 dex = 1, track.index = track.index, labels.cex = 0.75)
97
98 #-----
99 # Plot sequencing depth for MP
100 #-----
101
102 bed <- read.delim("MP.depth.bed", header = FALSE, stringsAsFactors = FALS
103 E)
104 colnames.bed) <- c("chr", "start", "end", "count")
105 bed$factoꖑ <- chr.lens$factoꖑ[match.bed$chr, chr.lens$chr]]
106 bed$count <- bed$count / (bed$end - bed$start)
107
108 # Apply limits
109 ylim <- c(0, 50) # Adjust based on sequencing depth
110 bed$count[bed$count > ylim[2]] <- ylim[2]
111 bed$count[bed$count < ylim[1]] <- ylim[1]
112
113 # Add new track for WP sequencing depth
114 track.index <- track.index + 1
115 circos.par("track.height" = track.height)
116 circos.track(bg.border = bg.border, track.margin = c(0.01, 0), factors =
117 chr.layout$factoꖑ, ylim = ylim)
118
119 # Plot the data as lines on the track
120 circos.trackLines(factors = bed$factoꖑ, x = rowMeans.bed[, c("start", "e
121 nd"))], y = bed$count, lwd = 1.2, col = col.orange)
122 circos.yaxis(side = "left", at=c(ylim[1], mean(ylim), ylim[2]), sector.in
123 dex = 1, track.index = track.index, labels.cex = 0.75)

```

```

118
119
120 #-----
121 # Plot SNP density
122 #-----
123
124 bed <- read.delim("snp.count.bed", header = FALSE, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)
125 colnames(bed) <- c("chr", "start", "end", "count")
126 bed$chr <- chr.lens$chr[match(bed$chr, chr.lens$chr)]
127
128 ylim <- c(0, 100) # Adjust based on SNP density.
129 bed$count[bed$count > ylim[2]] <- ylim[2]
130
131 # Add new track for SNP density
132 track.index <- track.index + 1
133 circos.par("track.height" = track.height)
134 circos.track(bg.border = bg.border, track.margin = c(0.01, 0), factors =
chr.layout$factors, ylim=ylim)
135
136 # Plot SNP density as rectangles
137 for(i in 1:nrow(chr.lens)){
138   dat <- bed[bed$chr == chr.lens$chr[i], ]
139   circos.rect(border = col.blue, xleft = dat$start, xright = dat$end, ybottom = 0, ytop = dat$count, col = col.blue, track.index = track.index, sector.index = chr.lens$factors[i])
140 }
141
142 circos.yaxis(side = "left", at = c(ylim[1], mean(ylim), ylim[2]), sector.index = 1, track.index = track.index, labels.cex = 0.75)
143
144
145 #-----
146 # Plot filtered SNP density
147 #-----
148
149 bed <- read.delim("snp_filter.count.bed", header = FALSE, stringsAsFactors = FALSE)
150 colnames(bed) <- c("chr", "start", "end", "count")
151 bed$chr <- chr.lens$chr[match(bed[, 1], chr.lens$chr)]
152
153 ylim <- c(0, 10) # Adjust based SNP density
154 bed$count[bed$count > ylim[2]] <- ylim[2]
155
156 # Add new track for SNP density
157 track.index <- track.index + 1
158 circos.par("track.height" = track.height)
159

```

```

160   circos.track(bg.border = bg.border, track.margin = c(0.01, 0), factors =
161   chr.layout$factores, ylim=ylim)
162   # Plot SNP density as rectangles
163   for(i in 1:nrow(chr.lens)){
164     dat <- bed[bed$chr == chr.lens$chr[i], ]
165     circos.rect(border = col.red, xleft = dat$start, xright = dat$end, ybot
166     tom = 0, ytop = dat$count, col = col.red, track.index = track.index, sect
167     or.index = chr.lens$factores[i])
168   }
169   circos.yaxis(side = "left", at = c(ylim[1], mean(ylim), ylim[2]), sector.
170   index = 1, track.index = track.index, labels.cex = 0.75)
171   #-----
172   # End the plot
173   #-----
174
175   dev.off()
176

```